

The greater area of the swamp is between 1,400 and 2,000 m altitude. Low night temperatures (sometimes below 11 °C) affect spikelet fertility.

We have isolated a variety from China, Yunnan 3, that yields well (3.5

t/ha) in the swamps at 1,400-1,650 m. But it is a typical japonica variety, while the local land races are indica type and nonglutinous. It also has partial sterility, noncoordinated tillering, long cycle, and susceptibility to *Pseudomonas*

fuscovaginae and *Pyricularia oryzae*.

IRRI breeding lines and Yunnan 3 were screened for low temperature tolerance in the Akagoma swamp (1,510 m) Dec-Jun. Percent sterility varied widely (see table).□

Effect of low temperature on yield and some agronomic characters of rice

N. M. Miah and M. S. Pathan, Plant Breeding Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Gazipur 1701, Bangladesh

We studied the effect of low temperature on 10 rice genotypes in irrigated rice, 1984 boro season. Two trials were conducted in the same plot. The first trial was seeded 31 Oct and transplanted 5 Dec 1983. The second trial was seeded 15 Nov and transplanted 20 Dec. Spacing was 25- × 15-cm in 5.4-m² plots, in a randomized complete block (RCB) design with 5 replications. Fertilizer was applied at 80-26.4-33.2-100-2.3 kg N, P, K, gypsum, and Zn/ha and normal management practices were followed.

Temperature at different crop stages, Feb-Apr 1984, BRRI, Bangladesh.

In the first trial, low temperature in Feb 1984 (see figure) coincided with panicle initiation. Low temperature resulted in significantly longer growth

duration, shorter plants and panicles, lower number of panicles/hill, higher spikelet sterility, and lower grain yield (see table).□

Effect of time of transplanting on yield and yield components in 2 irrigated transplanted rice trials.^a BRRI, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1984 dry season.

Entry	Duration (d)		Days to flowering		Plant height (cm)		Panicles (no./hill)		Panicle length (cm)		Spikelet sterility (%)		1000-grain weight (g)		Yield (t/ha)	
	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
BG35-2	171	163	150	142	71	87	10	11	22.6	23.4	26	13	23	24	3.7	4.9
BG367-4	169	163	146	140	80	90	9	11	18.4	19.0	22	19	19	19	3.5	4.7
MRC603-3-3	179	170	156	146	80	87	13	14	22.0	24.0	19	21	22	24	4.4	4.0
IR13429-196-1	172	164	150	141	74	78	11	11	22.0	22.6	21	19	22	23	3.8	4.2
IR36	181	170	158	147	72	75	12	14	19.7	20.8	20	17	20	21	4.2	5.5
IR50	170	160	144	137	63	73	14	14	18.5	20.0	28	22	20	20	4.1	4.9
IR9729-67-3	168	154	140	131	71	77	10	12	19.5	22.0	27	24	22	22	3.2	4.5
IR9828-91-2-3	177	169	154	145	69	75	13	15	19.4	21.4	18	17	21	21	3.8	4.0
Taichung sen yu 285	175	167	152	143	89	97	9	9	25.0	24.6	15	14	26	26	4.4	5.5
BR1	166	156	141	134	65	79	14	13	18.4	20.1	38	25	21	21	2.7	4.0
Average	173	164	149	141	73	82	11.5	12.4	20.5	21.8	23.4	20.1	21.6	22.1	3.8	4.6
<i>t</i> -value ^b (df8)	13.2**		17.8**		6.37**		3.1 *		4.5**		2.5**		2.2 ^{ns}		5.2**	

^a 1 = 31 Oct seeding, 2 = 15 Nov seeding. ^bSignificant at the 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels of probability.

The International Rice Research Newsletter is mailed free to individuals and institutions engaged in rice research and training. For further information, write IRRI, Communication and Publications Dept., Division R, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.